

The Problem and Difficulties Faced for All Sector Laborers in Karnataka State

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ABSTRACT:

The major labour problem is the economics term widely used toward the turn of the 21st century with various applications and the labour is physical and mental efforts any commodity are goods and service and include all types of efforts of economic situation and rewards of all active of factor of production and has been defined in many ways. Such as understandings the problem of improving the conditions all sector laborers in Karnataka it was employment of the wage-earning classes seeks to the labour law makes a distinction between people who work in “organized” sectors and represented entity to improve the socioeconomic statues and working conditions of the people. The working in “unorganized sectors” and include farming, construction work We can ensure that all laborers are able to access better wages, working conditions, and opportunities, and contribute to the growth and development of the all sector. challenges faced by all laborers requires a multi-pronged approach that involves improving working conditions, providing access to technology and education, and creating new opportunities for economic growth the labour problem encompasses the difficulties faced by wage-earners and employers who began to cut wages for various reasons including increased technology, desire for lower costs or to stay in our own business.

KEYWORDS:

Wage-earners, Legislative Efforts, Organized and unorganized sector.
Social justice, Measurement of Labour Force

Introduction

The labor problem encompasses the difficulties faced by wage-earners and employers who began to cut wages for various reasons including increased technology, always trying to maximize profits, machines were making the production process cheaper meaning wages took up a bigger percentage of costs, and when times were particularly tough, it made sense to cut wages to stay in business. Industrialization is considered to be one of the key engines to support the economic growth of any

country. The commence of industry and its growth is not a venture of the employer alone; yet it involves the hard work and tough grind of each and every stakeholder of the industry including the laborers, supervisors, managers and entrepreneurs. With the initiation of the concept of welfare state in the early realm of independence of our country, various legislative efforts have made their first move in the direction of welfare, equitable rights, social justice, social equity and equitable participation of the labour as a stakeholder at parity. A labour laws have been established to ensure elevated health, safety, and welfare of workers; to protectThis led to lower wages in the long run because fixed costs decreased (with increased technology) so employers saw fit to cut wage expenses for this now partially expendable labor force. Although the problem spanned many industries, they were not all concerned with the same problems Desire for lower costs or to stay in business. The wage-earning classes responded with strikes, by unionizing and by committing acts of outright violence.

Objective of the Study

- The purpose of this study is to understand the problems and prospects of all laborers in Karnataka
- To compare their problems with organized worker with the reference of labour laws of Karnataka
- To achieve harmonious industrial relations and quick settlement of disputes.

Research Methodology:

This study is based on secondary sources of data such as articles;ensure reliable, journals, books, websites and othersources.

Organized Labour Sector

Organized labour is an association of workers united as a single, representative entity to improve the economic status and working conditions of employees organized sector, which is registered with the government, is called an organized sector. In this sector, people get assured work, and the employment terms are fixed and regular.Workers and enterprises operating within a legal framework characterized by government regulation, formal registration, job security, fixed wages, and benefits like provident funds and paid leave. This contrasts with the unorganized sector,

which includes informal, unregistered businesses lacking legal protections and benefits for workers. Organized labour also refers to labor unions, which are associations of workers formed to improve their economic status and working conditions through collective bargaining with employers. A number of acts apply to the enterprises, schools and hospitals covered under the organized sector through collective bargaining with company management and security of employment.

Unorganized Labour Sector

The term unorganized worker has been defined under the unorganized workers' social security Act, 2008, as a home based worker, unorganized, and largely operates outside the control of the government. Employees in the unorganized sector do not have benefits such as overtime pay, sick leaves, etc. that the organized sector provides. Which includes workers in industries such as agriculture, construction, and domestic workers often lack formal contracts or legal protections, and may not have access to social security or benefits with consists of a vast, diverse workforce, often with low incomes, unstable employment, and no formal contracts or government protection. This sector is characterized by scattered, small-scale enterprises and family-run businesses, leading to challenges in implementing labor laws and a lack of organized representation or social security Self-employed worker or a wage worker in the unorganized sector and includes a worker in the organized sector who is not covered by any of the acts mentioned in Schedule.

Current problems faced by Labours in Karnataka

The Government too later on realized the gravity of the problem and could not remain a spectator for the workers constituted a large section of the society. Some of the new demands by labourers are an increase in minimum daily wages from Rs 360 to 460 for eight hours of work, besides introduction of benefits like bonus and provident fund. Labour unions insist that the guarantees may see a positive impact on workers' livelihood rather than create a crisis the government had to intervene to settle the disputes in the interest of national economy and the welfare of the society at large. If some key industry is thrown out of gear, the whole system is break downs of even a part of the economic system tend to impoverish the community in some cases; they face labour issues such as unsafe working conditions, poor living conditions, and unpaid salaries.

Labour problems constituted a serious menace to the society, and needed solution, if not to eradicate then at least to mitigate them in the very beginning. Employers paid their sole attention to the maintenance of machines and the improvement of the technical knowhow to the utter neglect of the human hands this is a form of employment in which an employee is forced to work with an employer due to the inability to repay the debt due to high-interest rates of Society, Social Service League and some industrial social workers raised their voice against these problems. To help in a stringent process of compliance and communication between employees, workers, trade unions, managers, and workshop representatives. That is why the labour laws in Karnataka provide for the rights and obligations of employees and companies in the workplace. It plays an important role in working in an organization and in regulating the rights and obligations of employers and working employees. They were successful in mobilizing the public opinion in support of their view point out of workers also started to form their own organization to fight against exploitation at the hands of industrialists. In the beginning the effort of the workers was not very successful because of their weak bargaining power and lack of resources on which they could rely for their livelihood in the absence of wages.

Some of the Important Labour Laws in Karnataka

The various labour laws in Karnataka, people provide their labor to businesses in exchange for wages, and they trade their unpaid leisure time for paid work time to make a living and to be able to purchase goods and services. Businesses, in turn, use this labor to produce goods and services demanded by consumers and along with the compliances to be made by the employer have been detailed below.

- Labour Department Act & Rules Labour Laws on Industrial Relations under the labour laws in Karnataka
- Minimum Wages Act 1948 under the labour laws in Karnataka
- Karnataka Trade Unions Regulations, 1958 Labour Laws On Social Security under the labour laws in Karnataka
- The Karnataka Payment of Wages Rules, 1963 under the Labour Laws in Karnataka
- The Karnataka Labour Welfare Fund Rules 1968 under the labour laws in Karnataka

- The Unorganized Workers Social Security Act 2008] Labour Laws On Wages under the labour laws in Karnataka
- Labour Laws On Working Conditions under the labour laws in Karnataka

Factors Affecting Measurement of Labour Force

This sector faces eventual deficiencies in regulations over employment, remuneration pattern, poor employer and employee relationship and casual work culture. Informal sector covers large number of workers from rural and substantial number from important to understand the forces shaping the structure of unemployment duration and its dynamics. Moreover, there is no absolute correlation across countries between the level of aggregate unemployment and its duration. Countries with very low unemployment do show low long-term unemployment rates and incidences, and the reverse is also true the urban areas by potentially engaging family labour and technology. The labours engage in casual, seasonal and scattered employments, which are not unionized. A large number of statutes addressing issues concerning unorganized sector are neither feasible nor practicable. Unorganized workers are also kept away from the Social Security Benefits such as Old Age Pensions, Gratuity, Employees State Insurance; Workmen's Compensation of the higher economic growth can be achieved through inclusive growth the informal economy. According to 15th International Conference of Labour Statisticians (1993) the informal sector are producing goods or services primarily for generating employment and incomes to the poor". Changing workforce demographics are challenging businesses to be more adaptive and inclusive. Employers must now consider the unique needs and perspectives of their employees to create a positive and productive workplace culture. More than 90 per cent of the total workforce in the country and 50 per cent of the total Net National Product are contributed by the socially and economically underprivileged sections of the society working in informal sectors.

Conclusion

The labour regulation relating to minimum wage, social security and welfare have increased miseries of informal sector. Lack of skills and training, home based work, micro enterprises, has created unregulated work environment. Non availability of jobs in the capital intensive organized sectors due technological advancement encourage employments in

the labour intensive unorganized sectors. Many are attracted to the all sector due to the easy employment and income. Government should regulate informal economic activities with safety and health. The causes for injuries, fatalities, diseases, disasters in this sector should be controlled. It provides for framing of schemes by the Central as well as state governments and funding of central government schemes. To achieve its objective, there is a provision for the constitution of the board at the State level and also the funding of all state government schemes for record keeping by district administration and for the setup of the workers facilitation centre. It empowers the governments at Central and State levels for framing the rules. The enterprises should focus to contribute to the national assets by creating community awareness on sensitive issues connected to worker.

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The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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